

A STUDY ON EMPLOYEE PERCEPTION, AWARENESS AND COMPLIANCE TOWARDS ENVIRONMENT FRIENDLY PRACTICES AT WORKPLACE

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the Study: The aim of the study is to identify the perception, awareness level of employees and compliance towards environment friendly practices at workplace.

Methodology: This study has been carried out at a Consultancy Firm in Bangalore named Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd. The 60 employees working at Empert Consultants have been assessed on their awareness and compliance level towards Environment Friendly Practices through a structured questionnaire.

Findings: The study concludes that the awareness levels are high however the implementation of practices that are eco-friendly needs to be more effective. The study also highlights the practices that could be brought in by organizations to become environment friendly organizations.

Practical Implications: Environment protection and conservation has been the most discussed issue across the world. The impact of environment degradation has become very prominent with recent calamities that has hit the planet. Protecting and conserving the environment is not the responsibility of the government alone, each and every human being needs to become aware and do his bit in protecting our natural resources and conserving nature.

Originality/Value: Organizations too have the social responsibility of developing practices which are environment friendly. Companies which are perceived to be environmentally conscious tend to have better brand image and are successful in attracting and retaining top talent. Developing practices that are environment friendly help an organization improve employee participation in environment conservation and protection.

Keywords: Environment Friendly Practices, Eco-friendly, Awareness, Social Responsibility, Protection, Conservation, Perception

Paper Type: Research Paper

1. INTRODUCTION

Global Warming has become the biggest concern for every country, every government, and every individual. The year that went by has been historic in terms of the way nature has behaved. Climate Change is evident and is impacting all aspects of human, plant, and animal life. The temperatures of our planet Earth have shown an incremental increase since 1981 and this sure is a warning signal of how dangerous things could get in future. The period from 2013 – 2021 rank as the warmest years till date. This temperature increase is seen in excessive and unseasonal rains, severe summers, and severe winters across the world.

It is time, we as citizens understand the responsibility of protecting and conserving the environment. Environment Protection and conservation is understood as the practice of protecting the natural environment by individuals, organizations, and governments. Conserving the environment is important for the future of human life and existence. Adopting environment friendly practices is one way to protect and conserve natural environment and a step to combat global warming. Organizations are taking initiative and coming up with sustainable practices that help in reducing the harm and at the same time conserve natural resources. Employees play an important role in making an organization environment friendly. Reducing use of plastic, carpooling, solar lighting, electric vehicles, paperless offices, organic products, recycling are some of the practices that can be adopted to promote environment protection.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The topic of Global Warming and Climate Change has been a topic of research for the past many decades. The literature presented here talks about the work undertaken by researchers to bring to light the role of employees, their opinion and perception with regards to environment friendly attitude of the organization. The first in this area is a study by (Vedat, Saman, & Hamad, 2022) that talks about the influence of an organization's environmental awareness policies on behavior of its employees. The study conducted in Irbil province of Iraq on 400 employees working in various organizations concluded that there is positive relationship between the environment friendly policies of an organization and the behavior of the employees working in them. The employees displayed high satisfaction and commitment levels when the policies followed were environment friendly.

Mendis & Indumathi, (2021) talk about the concept of 'Green Employee', 'Green Human Resource' and 'Green HRM'. The chapter talks about the importance of green consciousness in employees and also highlights the green practices followed in an organization. The writers mention 'Employee Green Behavior' as the conscious efforts put in by employees in making their workplace environment friendly. Green Consciousness of employees is seen as the need of the hour to make businesses sustainable and eco-friendly.

The study by (Asghar, Tahareh, & Najla, 2021) conducted on 196 employees working in 36 small sized units in Bangladesh talks about the benefit an organization and society can get when the employees display environmentally responsible behavior. The research arrived at the

conclusion that the employees who have high levels of positive psychological capital are able to behave in a responsible fashion. The researchers further add that when the employees are treated well at their respective workplace, they tend to present environmentally responsible behavior at their workplace.

In a book titled, “Industrial, Work and Organizational Psychology”, (Deniz S, Stephan, Brenton M, & Rachael M, 2018) talk about Employee Green Behavior as the environmentally responsible actions performed by employees in their individual jobs at workplace. The chapter presents ‘The Green Five Taxonomy’ which describes the green behavior of employees in five categories.

These five categories are transforming, conserving, avoiding harm, influencing others, and taking initiative. The researchers believe that employee behavior can be changed through a person-based approach and an intervention-based approach. Environment friendly behavior of employees can bring long term returns to the organization and society in general.

‘Being Green’ is becoming the norm in most of the well-known organizations across the world according to (Sweety, Aanchal, & Nupur, 2016). The paper talks about the strategies that can be implemented to make the workplace environment friendly. Adopting Green Management practices helps in enhancing public image, improves business efficiency, improved management – stakeholder relationship and enhanced utilization of human resources.

2.1 ENVIRONMENT FRIENDLY

The term Environment has been defined by Douglas and Hollandas “the external forces and influences that affect life, behavior and survival of living organisms”. In simple terms, our surroundings are what is referred to as Environment. Environment Protection and Conservation are terms that are often used interchangeably. Environment Conservation refers to the practice of humans saving the eco system from pollutants and human activities.

Glossary of Environment Statistics defines Environment Protection as “any activity to maintain or restore the quality of environment by preventing the emission and use of pollutants”. The credit of promoting Environment Conservation as a concept goes to Gifford Pinchot, who voiced his concern against the cutting of forests in the name of development. Environment Conservation involves all activities undertaken to conserve our natural resources and develop environment friendly practices.

The term ‘Environment Friendly’ refers to those products, services, guidelines, policies, laws and practices that has minimum or no negative impact on the eco system. Environment friendly practices determine the awareness levels of people towards environment protection and sustainability.

2.1.1 Methods of Environmental Conservation

The first and most important method of Conservation is *Forest Conservation*. Cutting down of trees in the name of development has been a major concern in towns and cities. Afforestation and Reforestation are the two ways of ensuring our forests are conserved for future generations. *Soil Conservation* is an important method of improving the soil quality and conserving the nutrients that will help in improving agricultural produce. Excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides must be discontinued, and Organic farming methods must be promoted.

Managing waste is another method to conserve our environment. Segregation of waste into Biodegradable and Non-Biodegradable is important for effective waste management. As individuals, it is essential to monitor our waste generation levels and ensure vermicompost pits are created and waste management system is put in place. *Recycling* is currently considered as the most important method for conserving our environment. Studies have reported that India generates 3.5 million tonnes of plastic waste annually which is a serious threat to animal and marine life. Covid-19 saw a surge in use of disposable containers and packaging materials which added to plastic waste generation. The Ban on Single use Plastic by Government of India is a big move in this regard.

Reducing Water Consumption is seen as an essential conservation technique as the water levels in freshwater lakes and wells are on a depleting trend. The use of water for domestic and industrial use has to be regulated and water recycling plants seem to be need of the hour. The Air Quality Index is an indicator of pollution in the air. Cities like Delhi, Mumbai have reported very poor Air Quality Index owing to high levels of vehicle emissions and industrial pollutants. *Controlling air pollution* is of paramount importance as it has a direct and immediate impact on human health.

Spreading Awareness is seen as the most essential method of conserving nature and natural resources. Awareness is the first step towards conservation. Media and Governance has to play an active role in creating awareness towards environment friendly practices.

2.1.2 Measuring Environmental Friendliness

Countries that engage in practices which cause minimal harm to environment are called Environment Friendly Countries. Such countries are ranked high on Environment Performance Index (EPI), a statistical method of rating countries on 32 Performance Indicators related to Environment policies and implementation of the same. This study is compiled by Yale University's Centre for Environmental Law and Policy. The EPI grades 180 countries on its environment friendliness and progress. India stands very low at 168th position on the EPI Index with a score of 27.60. The Top 10 countries according to their EPI Scores are as follows:

Table 1: Most Environment Friendly Countries 2022

Countries	EPI Ranking	EPI Score
Denmark	1	82.50
Luxemburg	2	82.30

Switzerland	3	81.50
United Kingdom	4	81.30
France	5	80.00
Austria	6	79.60
Finland	7	78.90
Sweden	8	78.70
Norway	9	77.70
Germany	10	77.20
India	168	27.60

Source: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/>

2.1.3 Environment Friendly Practices for the Workplace

A person spends majority of his or her time at workplace, and it is imperative that employees display responsible citizenship and follow environment friendly practices. Implementing sustainable practices in business and work life can be profitable and have a positive economic impact in the long run. Some of the common practices that can make the workplace environment friendly are switching to digital documentation, encouraging shared travel, promoting work from home, installing natural lighting, setting up indoor garden etc.

A study conducted by Porter Noveli Company indicates that 90% of Millennials and Generation Zers prefer to work for a company that is socially and environmentally responsible. In a report from Nielsen published in 2019, 81% of consumers felt that it was extremely important that companies must implement programs and practices to improve and conserve the environment. Such companies are also called as ‘Eco-Friendly Companies’ or ‘Green Companies’. The table below shows the 10 Companies of 2022 which are rated highest in terms of Environment Friendliness and Sustainability.

Table 2:Most Environment Friendly Companies 2022

Rank	Company	Area of Business	Contribution to Environment
1	Patagonia	Outdoor Clothing Company	Company has pledged 1% of sales for the past 35 years to environment conservation
2	Seventh Generation	Paper, Personal care and Cleaning Products Company	100% of their products and packaging uses biobased or post-consumer recycled material
3	A Good Company	E-commerce Company	Eco-friendly products and climate positive packaging

4	New Belgium Brewing	Craft Brewery	Platinum certified Zero Waste Business
5	Pela	Rubber & Plastic Products Manufacturing Company	World's 1 st 100% compostable phone case
6	Dr. Bronner's	Home Care Products	Organic & Fair-Trade Ingredients
7	Preserve	Personal Care Products	Sustainable products made from Recycled Plastic
8	Numi Organic Tea	Tea Manufacturing Company	The tea boxes are made of 90% post-consumer recycled content and their tea wrappers are now compostable.
9	Allbirds	Shoes & Apparel Company	Allbirds has pledged to bring their carbon footprint to zero.
10	Tentree	Apparel Company	Tentree plants 10 trees for every purchase of their sustainable and comfortable products.

Source: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/>

The big business houses can take pointers from the companies listed above and make their business environment friendly and display responsible corporate citizenship.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research paper is prepared with the following objectives:

- ✓ To understand the various aspects of Environment friendly practices followed at workplace across the globe
- ✓ To assess & analyze the employee perception, awareness level and compliance towards Environment friendly practices at workplace
- ✓ To suggest strategies to improve employee awareness and compliance levels

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The company selected for the study is Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd., a HR Consultancy firm located in Bengaluru, Karnataka. The Company is headquartered in Bangalore with offices across Bengaluru, Chennai, Hyderabad & Coimbatore. The company has a strong professional team with a joint experience of over 30 years in executive search. The company specializes in Leadership, Niche & Turn key hiring for SME, mid and large corporates, MNCs & family driven organizations. Mr. Vijay Venkatesh, the CEO of Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd., was awarded "Atmanirbhar Bharat Award-2022" on the occasion on 62nd National Summit of Indian Achiever's Forum held at New Delhi on 21st July 2022. The study has been conducted on 60 employees working at Bengaluru office. The study was conducted during the month of

September – October 2022. The study mainly focuses on understanding the perception, awareness level of employees about Environmental friendly practices. The study aims to analyze the employee and organization compliance towards environmental friendly practices.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Research Design is Descriptive in nature and aims to arrive at a deeper understanding of the employee perception, awareness, and compliance level towards environment friendly practices. The study involves employees working at Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd. Convenience Sampling Technique was used for choosing of 60 respondents. Both primary and secondary sources were used to collect information for the research paper. Structured Questionnaire was prepared and disseminated through Google Forms. The data was tabulated and analyzed to arrive at research outcome. One-way Anova was used to test the relationship between age of respondents and the level of awareness towards environment friendly practices.

6. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Table3: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Sl. No	Aspects	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Age		
a	20–25Years	42	70%
b	26–30Years	13	21.6%
c	31–35Years	04	6.7%
d	36 – 40 Years	01	1.7%
e	40&above	Nil	Nil
2	Gender		
a	Male	38	63.3%
b	Female	22	36.7%
3	Monthly Income		
a	Less than 10,000	22	36.7%
b	10,001to 25,000	19	31.7%
c	25,001to 50,000	15	25%
d	Above50,000	04	6.6%
4	Educational Qualification		
a	SSLC	Nil	Nil

b	PUC	01	1.7%
c	Graduate	17	28.3%
d	Postgraduate	42	70%
5	Marital Status		
a	Married	06	10%
b	Single	54	90%

Source: Primary Data

Based on the above table 3, we can summarize that 90% of the respondents chosen for study were single and were in the 20 – 30 years age bracket. The participation of Male respondents was more as compared to female respondents. The income level of respondents was slightly to the lower side, but their educational qualifications was on the higher side.

Table4: Respondent's Perception about Environment Friendly Practices at Workplace

Sl. No.	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1.	Organization prefers to maintain soft copy of documents	36.7%	31.7%	25%	6.6%	Nil
2.	Maintaining a garden at workplace is good for environment	36.7%	21.7%	28.3%	6.7%	6.6%
3.	Use of Natural Lighting at workplace is encouraged	21.7%	36.7%	33.3%	6.7%	1.6%
4.	Shared travel to workplace must be encouraged	35%	31.7%	33.3%	Nil	Nil
5.	Indoor Plants at workplace is environment friendly practice	40%	30%	30%	Nil	Nil
6.	Working from Home is Environment Friendly practice	20%	33.3%	33.3%	10%	3.4%
7.	Organization encourages employees to work from home	13.3%	36.7%	30%	15%	5%
8.	Excessive Documentation is hazardous for the environment	21.7%	41.7%	31.7%	3.3%	1.6%
9.	Organization uses Environment Friendly Furniture & Fixtures	16.7%	38.3%	40%	5%	Nil
10.	You are an Environment Friendly Responsible Employee	26.7%	33.3%	36.7%	1.7%	1.6%
11.	Organization is Committed towards conserving the	30%	33.3%	31.7%	3.3%	1.7%

	environment					
12.	E-friendly Practices improve Quality of Work Life	35%	36.7%	26.7%	1.6%	Nil

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 presents the Employees awareness and perception of environment friendly practices followed by them as individuals and those followed by organization. 62% of the respondents agreed that excessive documentation was harmful for the environment and 67% of them preferred to maintain documents in soft copy. 57% of respondents felt that maintaining a garden at workplace was good for the environment and 70% of them favored the idea of having indoor plants. When asked about type of lighting that could be used at workplace, 57% felt that Natural lighting was best for environment protection.

53% of the target respondents opined that working from home was an environment friendly practice, and 66% felt that shared travel must be encouraged to conserve fuel usage and reduce air pollution. When asked whether their organization supported the concept of working from home, only 49% replied in affirmative. 59% of the employees who participated in the survey felt that they were an Environment Friendly Responsible Employee. 54% of the employees chosen for study agreed that their company was making use of environment friendly furniture and fixtures. 63% of them felt that Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd. were committed towards conserving the environment. When asked whether E-friendly practices improve quality of work life, 71% responded positively.

Table5: Respondent's Compliance towards Environment Friendly Practices at Workplace

Sl. No	Statements	Always	Most of the Times	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1.	Practice of Car / Bike Pooling to workplace	15%	18.3%	38.3%	11.7%	16.7%
2.	Using Reusable Containers for Lunch	43.3%	26.7%	21.7%	5%	3.3%
3.	Using own Water Bottles & Coffee Mugs	38.3%	33.3%	21.7%	5%	1.7%
4.	Practice of Printing both sides of paper	35%	35%	26.7%	3.3%	Nil
5.	Using One side Printed Paper	33.3%	20%	31.7%	15%	Nil

6.	Using Designated Waste Bin for Disposal	38.3%	20%	31.7%	10%	Nil
7.	Using Handkerchiefs instead of Tissue Paper	28.3%	36.7%	30%	3.3%	1.7%
8.	Practice of turning off Computer Monitor during breaks	31.7%	31.7%	23.3%	11.7%	1.6%
9.	Practice of turning off Computer before leaving office	56.7%	16.7%	21.7%	3.3%	1.6%
10.	Encouraging Peers to follow environment friendly practices	28.3%	45%	25%	1.7%	Nil

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 highlights the level of compliance of employees in following environment friendly practices at workplace. Only 15% of respondents practices shared travel daily, however another 18% did do car and bike pooling on a frequent basis. 43% employees were bringing lunch in reusable containers and 38% were found using their own water bottles and coffee mugs at work. When asked whether the employees prefer to print on both sides of paper, 70% replied in affirmative and 33% also were practicing the habit of recycling one sided sheets.

54% of respondents practiced usage of handkerchief as against use of tissue paper, and 58% had good waste disposal habits. When asked whether they switch off their computers before leaving for the day, a good 56% said yes, but only 31% had the regular habit of turning off monitor during short breaks. 73% of respondents were regularly influencing their peers and friends to follow environment friendly practices at workplace and in their personal life.

6.1 Hypothesis Testing using One-way ANOVA

H0: There is a no significant relationship between age of respondents and their awareness level towards environment friendly practices

H1: There is a significant relationship between age of respondents and their awareness level towards environment friendly practices

Table 6: ANOVA: Single Factor

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
Age Group	60	85	1.416667	0.484463		
Awareness Level	60	105	1.75	0.936441		

ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	3.333333	1	3.333333	4.691849	0.032317	3.921478
Within Groups	83.83333	118	0.710452			
Total	87.16667	119				

Source: Primary Data

The result (P-value 0.03) which is lesser than 0.05 shows that there is a relationship between age of respondents and their awareness level towards Environmental Friendly Practices. So, Null hypothesis H_0 rejected. Alternative hypothesis H_1 is accepted for this which means the awareness towards environmental friendly practices is higher among the younger age employees.

7. CONCLUSION

The study at Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd., brings to light the perception, awareness, and compliance of employees towards environment friendly practices. The awareness level of employees is good however the compliance of environment friendly practices needs attention. The organization needs to come up with a plan with the involvement of employees to make Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd., the most environment friendly company. Modern companies and employees love to support brands that care about environment.

Hence, following eco-friendly practices the company can attract more loyal customers, which means bigger profits and greater chances of success. Developing an environment friendly organization begins at the lowest level, the employees need to be sensitized and made aware of conserving natural resources. Following environmentally friendly practices saves essential resources like power, water etc. Going Green has to be the motto of every employee and every organization. Encouraging environment friendly practices at workplace will result in healthy and happy employees and a successful and responsible organization.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

The call for employees and organizations to become environment conscious and friendly is growing stronger with every passing day. Corporates are starting to realize the enormous role they can play through their policies and practices in conserving our natural environment. We Work, the shared workplace company recently announced that it would not be serving meat-based products in its offices. Companies like Starbucks and Hyatt have banned use of plastic straws in its premises. A lot needs to be done to protect what we have in terms of nature and

natural resources. Some of the practices that could be implemented by the organization in question Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd., and many such organizations are as follows.

- Implementing a robust Recycling program is key to being environment friendly. All kinds of waste must be segregated and recycled at workplace. Employees must be made aware of minimizing waste generation and optimum waste management.
- Conserving energy is the second most important initiative towards conservation of natural resources. A strict policy regarding usage of equipment, lighting systems must be in place and implemented effectively. Switching to natural lighting can go a long way in energy conservation.
- Moving to Paperless Office is a right move towards environment friendliness. Adopting Digital and Cloud computing solutions can help in documentation and reducing use of paper. Digital records are far easier to manage and store for future reference.
- Employers must encourage sustainable transportation in the form a bicycle ride or using public transport or at least carpooling to work. Allowing employees to work from home is also a good move towards reducing traffic and emission related issues.
- Engaging in environment friendly CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) activities using the workforce is yet another strong initiative. Employees from Generation Z are extremely conscious and are eager to do their bit in preserving the environment. This drive must be channelized in the right direction.
- ‘Going Green’ needs to become a part of the corporate culture. Employee involvement and participation at every stage will help in making the most of this concept. Employees must imbibe within them the urgency and importance of following environment friendly practices whilst at work and whilst at home.

9. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The study dwells on the topic of environment friendly practices at workplace. The study is limited only to opinion shared by employees working at Empert Consultants Pvt. Ltd., Bengaluru. Hence, the scope is not wide enough. The responses could have an element of bias as the employees might have hidden facts or details. The number of responses is also limited to 60 employees. Thus, the study covers a limited geographical area and limited number of people. There is potential for this topic to be researched on a larger scale and bigger audience. Future studies could be undertaken to understand perception, awareness and compliance at an industry or sector level.

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